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Authors: Yvonne Höller, Aljoscha Thomschewski, Leon Dađi Sesseljasson, Sven Rothlübbers, Jürgen Jenne, Laura Astolfi, Ren Xu, Marc Fournelle

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PU	Public	X
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

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Overview and scope of this document

This document provides the clinical specification of the novel EEG-US device, based on an assessment of clinical requirements from stakeholders. Clinical constraints were extracted and use cases and workflows were defined. The development of this document took place in a constant exchange between the clinical team (UNAK, CDK) and the technical development team (UROME, GTEC, MEVIS, IBMT) realized in online, bi-weekly meetings.

Version history

2023-05-20 Initial Version

2023-05-31 Final Version

Stakeholder Analysis

After a thorough research on clinical practices in 43 countries (Argentina, Australia, Belgium, Brazil, Bulgaria, Canada, Croatia, Denmark, Egypt, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Iceland, Ireland, Israel, Italy, Japan, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Mexico, Monaco, New Zealand, Nigeria, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Saudi Arabia, Serbia, Slovenia, South Africa, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine, United Arab Emirates, United Kingdom, United States), we found that different countries involve different experts in the various tasks that the system might be used for (see File "User groups.xlsx"). The professions named in the analysed countries for various tasks that are related to the future use of the innovation are as follows:

- **recording EEG data:** electrocardiology technician, lab technician, neurologist, EEG technician, clinical neurophysiologist, neurophysiology specialist, nurse assistance, neurophysiopathologist, nurse specialised in EEG, technologist, biomedical technician, physician, specialist in neurology, psychiatrist, neurophysiology technician
- **interpreting EEG data:** neurologists, neurophysiologists, functional diagnostics physician, neurophysiopathologist, neurology specialist, specialised consultant, clinical neurophysiologist, neurophysiology technician

From these professions, we extracted relevant groups, supplemented by further stakeholders that are relevant for the future exploitation of the innovation.

Patients

Roles: Will be diagnosed/treated with the new system

Responsibility: Have to attend appointments with health care professionals. As long as the device is not a standard equipment in diagnostics, informed consent of the patient is needed. For intervention (stimulation), patients might always have to give informed consent.

Main task goals: Want comfortable, risk-free or low-risk, brief, available examinations that lead to clear diagnosis or provide effective treatment

System skills and experience: No skills, training, qualifications needed

Physical limitations: Wounds on scalp; implants (i.e. electronic such as VNS or magnetic such as surgical implants); possibly: cardiovascular limitations, respiratory pumps, limitations posed by weight of the system (has implications for usability in children and cervical patients).

Cognitive abilities: able to give informed consent / have a representative that gives informed consent for treatment (always relevant, but more relevant for stimulation); for "resting state" acquisition no collaborative abilities are needed, for functional imaging linked to cognitive tasks ability to complete the tasks is required

Motivation and attitude: Patient must be motivated to get treatment and for functional imaging must be motivated to complete the tasks that are used to activate specific brain regions

Physicians

Roles: Diagnose/Treat patients

Responsibility: Safety and best possible treatment for patient; weigh out risks and benefits of treatment/diagnosis.

Main task goals: Want clear diagnostic/interventional benefits from the new system, high availability (hospitals should have it), easy to use, data is easy to access

System skills and experience: For treatment: Neurostimulation experience required. For imaging: Must be experienced in reviewing neurological images in general and specifically those produced by this system, therefore:

Training: training on reviewing the produced images required; stimulation: training required (e.g. for EEG "license" a specific number of EEGs must have been recorded/reviewed)

Task knowledge: Must be aware of the possibilities and limitations of the system/imaging/stimulation process, need to know adverse event possibilities and profile of counterindications for treatment/measurement.

Qualifications: MD in the respective field (Neurology, possibly Neurosurgery...)

Motivation and attitude: Must be motivated to get training and use new system

Medical technicians

Roles: Assist in conducting the examination instead of/in addition to physicians (depends on responsibilities, which vary by country)

Responsibility: Safety of patient during examination, complete assigned procedure of neuroimaging according to system specification

Main task goals: Complete assigned procedure of neuroimaging – will most likely not be involved in stimulation. Want easy to use, time efficient tool, needs little training to be used

System skills and experience: Must be trained on the use of the system for acquiring images

Task knowledge: Prior knowledge on acquisition of EEG/neuroimages/ultrasound beneficial; Need to know counterindications for treatment/measurement.

Training: Must be trained on the system

Qualifications: According to country's legal system of licensed professionals in the field

Physical and cognitive abilities: Covered by license of the profession

Motivation and attitude: Must be motivated to learn new system / take on new tasks in addition to what they are used to so far. Interest in research is beneficial

Hospitals/health care provider

Roles: Provide infrastructure and staff for patient management

Responsibility: Keep infrastructure available, up-to-date, and maintained

Main task goals: Provide diagnosis and treatment that is cost effective, needs little staff and space, equipment should have a decent amount of mobility (is easy to move), has low maintenance costs, and is sustainable (time until repair/replacement is needed)

Motivation and attitude: Motivation to provide up-to-date and best treatment, motivation to minimize costs (relevant when new system is more cost effective)

Financial stakeholders e.g. public and private health insurances

Roles: Manage finances that are provided by health insurance system and provide them to the health care professionals/institutions according to treatment needs of patients.

Responsibility: Cover costs according to best practice guidelines – do not spend financial resources on unnecessary procedures but cover necessary and meaningful interventions.

Main task goals: Aims for low costs of equipment and procedures, need certifications for use (differ between countries, e.g. FDA approval etc.)

Motivation and attitude: Motivation to invest available financial resources cost-effectively; Questions to ask: What is needed to approve a new tool for routine use? What costs are feasible?)

Scientists

Roles: Investigate new application areas of the system, brain activity correlates of cognitive processes, abnormalities in patients etc.

Responsibility: Ethical use of the tool in terms of participant safety and science ethics (reliability and validity of acquired data and its analysis and interpretation)

Main task goals: Answer research questions, test research hypotheses; make new discoveries that can be published

System skills and experience: Must be trained on the use of the system and analysis of the data

Task knowledge: Prior knowledge on acquisition of brain signals e.g. EEG and/or fMRI beneficial, need to know about artifacts and biases that might hamper data quality/validity

Training: Must be trained on the system

Qualifications: Similar to EEG recordings that with little training, acquisition of data should be possible soon independently (e.g. after 3 recordings under supervision), but more extensive knowledge is needed for (advanced) data analysis beyond qualitative data review. Cognitive examinations are often done by psychology researchers, but other disciplines such as computer science (e.g. “fingerprint of the brain”), sports science etc. are likely to be interested as well.

Physical and cognitive abilities: Similar to EEG, e.g. the acquisition for people in a wheelchair is possible but problematic. Usually, both hands are needed.

Motivation and attitude: Must be motivated to learn and use a new system – motivation usually high

Tasks

Imaging

Neurology

Record imaging/EEG data for later expert review and/or storage and/or do on-line reviewing i.e. review data while it is being recorded (delay of recording to display of a couple of seconds is acceptable) in the acute or ambulatory setting, e.g. acute: status epilepticus, stroke. Ambulatory: quick imaging modality in style of e.g. US of blood vessels in the neck – in both cases physician reviews data during acquisition.

Possible Outputs: Activity map of whole brain/specific brain regions in relation to neurological phenomena e.g. epileptic spikes seen in the EEG or status epilepticus, sleep stages, stroke, brain tumour
Differential images of brain/specific brain regions between two different conditions (e.g. baseline vs. during epileptic spikes)

Duration of tasks: e.g. a clinical routine EEG acquisition usually takes 20min, sleep EEG takes at least 8h, up to 24h EEG monitoring for several days (e.g. epilepsy monitoring) as the max. possible requirement

Science

Research Questions to be answered via functional imaging for functional analysis: Does activation in brain region x correlate with cognitive ability y or brain disorder z? Does timing of activation in brain region x correlate with cognitive ability y or brain disorder z? Does interaction of activation between brain regions w and x correlate with cognitive ability y or brain disorder z?

Possible outputs: numeric data that can be processed statistically e.g. for volume analysis or comparison of activation status in different conditions (baseline vs. cognitive activation)

Duration of Tasks: varies from a couple of minutes to 2 hours / 12 hours for over-night recordings of EEG (duration might also be limited by ability of research participants to focus/motivation to participate)

Stimulation

Neurology

For treatment

Low intensity stimulation e.g. like TMS for activating/deactivating brain regions.

Differentiation between single treatment sessions or repeated treatments according to plan (implications for safety and comfort of patients as well as adaptiveness of stimulation schemes).

Possible outputs: improvement of clinical symptoms, e.g. epileptic activity

Duration of tasks: Need to be determined in terms of clinical efficacy

For diagnosis

Low intensity stimulation e.g. like TMS for activating/deactivating brain regions and obtaining a response such as motor evoked potentials in TMS, epileptic activity induced/suppressed by US stimulation

Possible outputs: Response map, Response curve.

Duration of tasks: 20-60min seem plausible

Science

TMS-like activation/deactivation of specific brain regions:

Deactivation: lesion-like studies

Activation: Neuroenhancement studies

Possible outputs: similar to neuroimaging, a map of responses to stimulation; behavioural reactions to stimulation depending on stimulation sites

Duration of tasks: Depends on the paradigm, 20-120min are most common

Processes

Install system in existing environment

Requirements

System needs to be compatible with available electricity (i.e. country specific; grounding and shielding); system needs to be compatible with other medical devices and tools (heart monitor, oxygen monitoring; respiratory pumps; VNS; pacemaker; stroboscopic stimulation device). System needs to be mobile if full potential shall be sought (i.e. ICU) --> space requirements. Specific local security measures need to be considered (i.e. anticonvulsive medication; backup generating set)

Tasks

Install system hardware using the existing space (best case) without disturbing other diagnostic medical tools. e.g. place system in the EEG lab of the hospital/scientific institution; Install other relevant software that can be run without interfering with the system's software.

Possible scenario

Technician from distributor (company selling the system) comes to hospital/ research institute and installs hard- and software; OR: detailed user manual allows easy setup (e.g. research EEG systems are often set up by researchers themselves, clinical EEG systems are always installed by the distributor)

Prepare patients/participants for recording

Requirements

System needs to be adaptable to different patients (head size; hair; allergies; implants; weight and height); set-up needs to be easy and fast.

Patients might be sitting as for EEG recordings – for some EEG recordings lying on a bed is required – this puts pressure on the recording contacts on the back of the head / neck roll might help.

Tasks

Turn system on, prepare head and hair (some EEG manufacturers recommend washing the hair before recording to remove grease); put cap on patient's/participant's head; prepare contacts with gel (e.g. degreasing, applying conductive gel – EEG and US gels differ significantly from each other – but solutions that can be used for both purposes are available), connect cap to hardware; check and adjust electric impedances and acoustic coupling;

View data on-line, check plausibility e.g. artefacts; afterwards: remove system, clean head, clean system

Further Considerations

Can injuries be inflicted while setting up the patient (such as irritated skin when using abrasive gel for EEG)? What cleaning (e.g. of the patient) is required afterwards? Are there patient constraints (physical, hair style, medical)? Most important: comfort of the patient and set-up time (max 20min recommended). Important for usage intraoperatively: system needs to be sterile; intra-operative use is very unlikely - more likely: pre-operative evaluation e.g. to determine epileptic focus

Record/view data

Requirements

Computational system to run software and write data. Data storage needs to be sufficiently large and fast.

Tasks

Choose saving directory (default directory should be available), initiate recording (with initiation saving starts automatically, e.g. buffered data is written to saving directory in regular time-intervals), monitor recording on-line on a screen, possibly: anonymize and export data.

Further Considerations

Is special hardware required to run software, save data and visualize data for live monitoring (computers, screens, storage devices); how long does it take to save data/terminate recording --> impacts frequency of recordings.

Conduct cognitive tasks during recording

Requirements

System must be connected with a computer/device that delivers visual, auditory, or tactile stimuli to the participant/patient and that records reactions e.g. button presses etc. From the participant/patient; These markers should be co-registered with the recorded EEG/US data such that the time-stamp of the markers is available in the EEG/US data and can be used for later averaging/event-related data processing; markers should be visible/confirmed in the on-line view of the recording such that it can be verified that they are saved/registered appropriately

Tasks

Prepare cognitive/sensory tasks in a script/software e.g. psychopy, psychtoolbox for Matlab, presentation, e-prime etc.

Connect presentation computer with EEG/US recording computer

Start EEG/US recording

Start experiment on presentation computer

Stimulation

Requirements

System needs to be set up and properly contacted to the patient. More than in functional recordings, a correlation must be built between a clinical pre-scan, e.g. MRI or CT and the layout of the transducers and brain scans, i.e. proper registration is necessary.

Tasks

Possible prerequisite: Record EEG without stimulation to obtain standard activity in cognitive task.

Choose intensity and location based on planning scans. Intensity should be within safety limits.

Start stimulation manually by defining duration and e.g. clicking start OR start a stimulation protocol e.g. repetitive stimulation at 0.5 Hz or similar.

Record EEG while US-stimulation takes place, i.e., start recording and have a trigger marker in the EEG when US-stimulation begins and ends.

Time markers and stimulation parameters (location, intensity, duration) for the stimulation should be recorded with the data such that data can be analyzed time-locked to the onset and duration of the stimulation.

Visualize result, e.g., response curve, e.g. average map of stimulation responses in the brain

Further Considerations

Only low-intensity stimulation is available without special precautions. e.g. it could be required to enter a special password or similar to activate the higher intensities but is not foreseen in the present project. (It may be necessary to design the system in such a way that it in any case only produce low intensity stimulation. This may aid in approval processes.)

Do additional patient restrictions apply? Are requirements regarding the environment different? Is a special power source or amplifier required?

Can stimulation impact other systems? Are special security measures required (to be answered by study)?
Legal issue.

Clean system/maintenance

Requirements

In clinical environments, disinfection is required, while more simple cleaning to remove contact gel and grease is sufficient for scientific use (see more details in D1.2 - Methods Specification).

Maintenance of hardware and software components.

Customer support is necessary for every hard- and software used in a clinic, to respond promptly to system failures that required intervention. If software updates are required (e.g. because of updates on the OS on which the software is running), it is usually the customer support to take care of those (very rarely the IT department of a hospital might take on responsibility of this task).

Process/analyse/interpret data

Requirements

Computational power; size of data (e.g. working memory requirements of computing facilities?) Therefore: Is specific hardware required? Compatibility with other programs, i.e. can data be exported to generic data format for further processing with e.g. python, matlab etc. can scripts for automatization be implemented. How many steps are required to preprocess data for clinical interpretation? Is visualization easy to accomplish, is all relevant information displayed to interpret the data?

Tasks - clinical

Preprocess data; e.g. artefact review, filtering, change montage view (clinical EEG view is often the “double banana” etc. While scientists prefer the common reference or average reference; Review data by “clicking through it”; Annotate data e.g. put markers into the data to indicate beginning of seizure, abnormalities, or to mark spikes etc.; Save annotations; Automated analysis e.g. average maps for specific events such as marked spikes, or response maps to stimulation

Tasks – science

Export EEG-data into another program for further analysis? (We do not expect this project to yield also a software for EEG data analysis).

Neuroimaging EEG-US data could be exported as well, but some visualization abilities by the software are highly desired e.g. for export of figures etc.

Further Considerations

Most important: time required of manual labor; accuracy and comprehensiveness of results. Clinical review should take minimal time (clinicians review and annotate 20min of EEG data in a couple of minutes, e.g. <5min)

Will special training be necessary to clinically interpret results? Can misinterpretations be harmful to patients? Can data be displayed in connection with other imaging findings (i.e. head solutions/co-registration with structural images from MRI)?

Use cases

Scientist collects data in connection with a cognitive task

Before the participant arrives the researcher (technician...) checks if the system is set up correctly. The researcher turns on the recording computer and the stimulus computer and makes sure they are correctly connected. The participant arrives and takes a seat. The researcher starts by asking the participant if they need to go to the bathroom before they start as it will be more difficult to do so once the testing has begun. Make sure that the participant is not using chewing gum and phones should be turned off or placed further away from the system. The researcher measures the participants head with a measuring tape. First the circumference of the head is measured where the radius of the head is the largest. This determines what size of cap should be used. Next the head is measured from ear to ear, the researcher has to make sure that the measurement is made from the same spot on both ears so that the measures are symmetrical. Once the measurement has been made the midpoint is taken to indicate where electrode Cz of the cap should be located. Next the length from the nasion to the inion is measured. The researcher marks a dot on the participant's forehead that is above the nasion by 10% of the distance measured between the nasion and the inion. The dot is marked by a marker that washes off easily (such as an eyeliner or eyebrow pencil).

Once the measurements have been done an EEG/US cap that fits the measurements is selected. The dot that was marked on the participant's forehead is used as a reference point and should be in line with electrodes Fp1 and Fp2. Once the cap has been situated on the participant's head with the marked dot in the right place relative to the corresponding electrodes, the researcher holds the front of the cap in place (or asks the participant to hold it in place) and pulls the cap from behind until it is firmly placed on the participant's head. The researcher then asks the participant if the cap feels comfortable, if they feel it is uncomfortable or too tight, the researcher may try a different size. The participant will need to wear the cap for an extended period of time and it is important that they do not feel uncomfortable. Next the participant is told to strap the cap on with straps that run along their neck. The participant is advised to strap it on as tightly as possible while still being relatively comfortable. Then the researcher places the 'loose' electrode on the participants cheek using some sort of adhesive tape, before the electrode is placed, a small amount of electrolyte is placed on the participants cheek (right below the eye) and on the electrode itself. The researcher then checks if the measurements are still correct, such that electrode Cz is midway between the ears and that the dot is in line with electrodes Fp1 and Fp2. Once the cap is on the head, it is plugged in and connected to the amplifier. When plugging the cap in, the researcher makes sure that the arrows marked on the cables of the cap and the amplifier meet each other.

Next the researcher uses a syringe to place small amounts of electrolyte /US-gel into small circular openings of the EEG/US cap. Once the researcher has inserted electrolyte into each electrode/sensor opening he/she inserts a q-tip into the electrode opening and moves it from side to side. It is preferable

to avoid twisting the q-tip in circles as it can create tangles in their hair. Rather it may be better to move the q-tip from side to side, and up and down. Once this has been done to each electrode/sensor opening, a little more electrolyte is added to each electrode/sensor opening and the process is repeated. Next the researcher checks the impedances on the recording software. They first check the highest possible range, if all the electrodes are below the desired threshold (e.g. $<20\text{k}\Omega$) they can move on to a lower range. If the electrodes are not in or at least close to the desired range, the researcher can add a little more electrolyte to that electrode opening and rubs it with the q-tip. This is then repeated for each electrode until they are all below/close to threshold. Then the researcher can move on to a lower threshold, typically $10\text{k}\Omega$, and repeat the process. The reference and the ground are also checked and should ideally be below $5\text{k}\Omega$.

(Maybe: once the electrolyte has been placed into the electrode openings the ultrasound gel is placed in the openings in the cap that are relevant for the ultrasound, there will be separate openings in the cap for the electrolyte and the ultrasound gel and they will be clearly marked to distinguish between the two).

Once a satisfying connection has been established the recording is turned on and the task begins. Once the task is finished the researcher turns off the recording and saves it. Then the cap can be unplugged from the amplifier and the powerpack can be turned off and plugged back in. The researcher then removes the tape that was holding the electrode in place on the participant's cheek and slowly removes the cap. This should be done carefully as the electrolyte can get stuck in the participants hair and cause some mild discomfort for the participant if it's not done carefully. The participant is then advised to wash their hair and is provided with shampoo and a towel. Lastly the EEG/US cap is washed thoroughly. The cap may be submerged into water but be careful not to submerge the cables. A little bit of baby shampoo is added to the water and a small brush such as a toothbrush is used to rinse the electrolyte from each electrode opening. The cap is then hung to dry.

EEG/US-technician records data for later review by clinician

General procedure similar to the scientist's use case. EEG/US technician prepares system before patient arrives. Patient arrives and takes a seat. EEG/US cap is put on the head, the specific gel is applied to the skin under the EEG and US sensors. The technician checks impedances/data quality to ensure high-quality recordings. In classical EEG recordings, a fixed procedure is followed, e.g.

- Rest with eyes open and eyes closed
- Hyperventilation
- Encourage patient to take a nap (20min)
- Photostimulation

During the recording, data is continuously displayed for quality purposes, so the technician can improve e.g. electric impedances. The data is saved and the clinician / person in charge for review is notified that it is available.

The clinician who performs the review accesses the data in a review software, scrolls through the data and looks for normal activity (e.g. in the EEG: Alpha blocking effect, slowing in response to hyperventilation) abnormalities (e.g. hemispheric differences, local slowing, epileptiform activity) at rest and in response to stimulation. A report is dictated/written and the data is archived.

EEG-technician sets system up and clinician joins to review data on-line to appraise acute status of patient (e.g. stroke, status epilepticus...)

General procedure similar to the scientist's use case. Acute patient is possibly unconscious and most likely lies on a bed. EEG-technician sets up the system and displays ongoing activity on a screen. Clinician is called to look at the monitor and diagnose acute condition of the patient in the online display, e.g. identifying patterns of a status epilepticus or similar. Clinician draws conclusions, e.g. to treat patient intravenously with sedative to stop the seizure. Patient will be disconnected from the system when intervention was successful, or when patient needs to be sent to another department for more intensive treatment. Data is saved and archived.

Application scenarios in terms of brain areas / clinical and scientific relevance

The advantage of the system is that it combines EEG, which has a high time-resolution, with US, which will allow to record functional images from deeper brain regions. In order to understand the practical relevance of imaging, a spreadsheet with a list of brain regions and related disorders / brain functions is provided in the Supplementary file "Brain regions.xlsx", including for example the temporal lobe which is relevant for temporal lobe epilepsy, the Broca area which is relevant for speech e.g. after stroke, the hypothalamus with several basic functions connected to it (e.g. control of hormones, long-term regulation of hunger, ...), the insula including important areas for taste, or the amygdala which is a core region in emotion processing, most prominently fear.

Supplementary Material

Regions of Interest

Localization in the brain by function

WORKING MEMORY	DECLARATIVE MEMORY	PROCEDURAL MEMORY	CONSCIOUSNESS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prefrontal cortex • Lateral intraparietal cortex (area LIP) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the medial temporal lobe (the hippocampus, entorhinal cortex, perirhinal cortex, parahippocampal cortex, fornix) • the diencephalon (the papez circuit, dorsomedial thalamus, mammillary bodies) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • basal ganglia (the striatum) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The cortex (the prefrontal and posterior occipital cortices and the claustrum) • Hindbrain • The paraventricular nucleus
DECISION MAKING	PERCEPTION AND SENSATION	SOCIAL COGNITION	INTELLIGENCE
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prefrontal Cortex (PFC) • Hippocampus 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • neocortex • thalamus • Vision: occipital lobe, posterior parts of temporal and parietal lobes, primary visual cortex • Hearing: auditory areas of the temporal lobes, auditory cortex 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Amygdala • posterior superior temporal sulcus • Orbital frontal cortex • Temporal cortex • Medial prefrontal cortex • Paracingulate cortex • Temporo-parietal junction • Temporal poles 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • frontal lobes • parietal lobes

EMOTION

- The Papez circuit/limbic system (cingulate cortex, hypothalamus, hippocampus, fornix, anterior thalamus)
- Amygdala (fear)
- Orbitofrontal cortex
- Stress: hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis (adrenal cortex, paraventricular nucleus of the hypothalamus, amygdala, hippocampus)

LANGUAGE

- Temporal lobes (especially in the left hemisphere)
- Broca's area
- Wernicke's area
- The arcuate fasciculus
- The angular gyrus
- Motor cortex

SLEEP

- Suprachiasmatic nuclei (SCN)

RESTING STATE

- Medial prefrontal cortex
- Posterior cingulate cortex
- Posterior parietal cortex
- Hippocampus
- Lateral temporal cortex

DEFAULT MODE NETWORK

- Anterior medial prefrontal cortex
- Posterior cingulate cortex
- Angular gyrus

ATTENTION

- Sensory areas (lateral geniculate nucleus (LGN))
- Visual cortical areas in the parietal and temporal lobes
- Posterior parietal cortex
- Pulvinar nucleus
- Frontal eye fields (FEF)
- Lateral intraparietal cortex (area LIP)

Brain location and clinical manifestation

CORTEX	FRONTAL LOBES	TEMPORAL LOBES
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tourette's • Body Dysmorphic disorder • Conversion disorder • Conversion disorder • Anorexia Nervosa • Bulimia Nervosa • Binge-Eating disorder • Insomnia disorder • Alcohol Use disorder • Huntington's disease • Alzheimer's disease • Lewy body dementia • Frontotemporal dementia • Autism (temporoparietal cortex) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tourette's • Schizophrenia • Bipolar • Body Dysmorphic disorder - inferior frontal cortex • Dissociative Identity disorder • Anorexia Nervosa • Enuresis (medial and inferior frontal gyrus) • Insomnia disorder • Oppositional Defiant disorder (medial superior frontal gyrus) • Conduct disorder (left medial superior frontal gyrus) • Alcohol Use disorder • Narcissistic Personality disorder • Frontotemporal dementia • Trichotillomania (Right inferior frontal gyrus) • Autism (Inferior frontal gyrus, Broca's area) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Schizophrenia • Bipolar • Body Dysmorphic disorder (occipito-temporal cortex) • Conversion disorder • Pica • Antisocial Personality disorder (superior temporal gyrus) • Frontotemporal dementia (anterior temporal poles) • Autism (temporoparietal cortex, Wernicke's area, superior temporal sulcus) • Schizotypal disorder (Superior temporal gyrus)

PARIETAL LOBES

- Bipolar
- Body Dysmorphic disorder (right parietal cortex)
- Dissociative Identity disorder
- Insomnia disorder
- Huntington’s disease (angular gyrus)

OCCIPITAL LOBE

- Bulimia Nervosa
- Binge-Eating disorder

PREFRONTAL CORTEX

- ADHD
- Schizoaffective disorder
- Bipolar
- Premenstrual Dysphoric disorder
- Anxiety disorders
- Dissociative Amnesia
- Somatic Symptom disorder
- Conversion disorder
- Conduct disorder
- Antisocial Personality disorder
- Alcohol Use disorder

AMYGDALA

- Autism
- Alcohol Use disorder
- Bipolar
- Major Depressive disorder
- Dysthymia
- Anxiety disorders
- Body Dysmorphic disorder
- Dissociative Identity disorder
- Conversion disorder
- Bulimia Nervosa
- Binge-Eating disorder
- Insomnia disorder
- Oppositional Defiant disorder
- Conduct disorder
- Antisocial Personality disorder
- Borderline Personality disorder

HIPPOCAMPUS	ANTERIOR CINGULATE CORTEX (ACC)	THALAMUS	HYPOTHALAMUS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Autism • Schizoaffective disorder • Bipolar • Major Depressive disorder • Dysthymia • Anxiety disorders • Dissociative Identity disorder • Dissociative Amnesia • Insomnia disorder • Antisocial Personality disorder • Borderline Personality disorder • Huntington's disease • Alzheimer's disease • Lewy body dementia • Temporal lobe Epilepsy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Autism • ADHD • Bipolar • Premenstrual Dysphoric disorder • Obsessive-Compulsive disorder (OCD) • Hoarding disorder • Excoriation (Skin-Picking) disorder • Somatic Symptom disorder • Insomnia disorder • Oppositional Defiant disorder (anterior cingulate gyrus) • Antisocial Personality disorder • Alzheimer's disease (cingulate gyrus) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tourette's • Schizotypal disorder • Schizophrenia • Major Depressive disorder • Dysthymia • Conversion disorder • Insomnia disorder • Alcohol Use disorder • Borderline Personality disorder • Huntington's disease • Frontotemporal dementia 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tourette's • Anxiety disorders • Narcolepsy • Alcohol Use disorder • Borderline Personality disorder • Huntington's disease

MIDBRAIN	ORBITOFRONTAL CORTEX (OFC)	STRIATUM	INSULA
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tourette's • Conversion disorder • Enuresis • Schizoaffective disorder (Ventral tegmental area) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Autism • Obsessive-Compulsive disorder(OCD) • Conduct disorder • Antisocial Personality disorder 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bipolar • Body Dysmorphic disorder • Excoriation (Skin-Picking) disorder • Anorexia Nervosa • Bulimia Nervosa • Binge-Eating disorder • Oppositional Defiant disorder • Conduct disorder • Huntington's disease • Parkinson's disease 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Autism • Body Dysmorphic disorder • Hoarding disorder • Conversion disorder • Anorexia Nervosa • Bulimia Nervosa • Binge-Eating disorder • Oppositional Defiant disorder • Conduct disorder

BASAL GANGLIA <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Autism • ADHD • Tourette's • Restless Legs Syndrome • Frontotemporal dementia 	INSULAR CORTEX <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Anxiety disorders • Narcissistic Personality disorder • Frontotemporal dementia 	ADRENAL CORTEX <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Anxiety disorders 	PRECUNEUS <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Insomnia disorder • Oppositional Defiant disorder • Conduct disorder
SUBSTANTIA NIGRA <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Huntington's disease • Parkinson's 	BRAIN STEM <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Insomnia disorder • Central Sleep Apnea • Frontotemporal dementia 	CAUDATE NUCLEUS <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Autism • Obsessive-Compulsive disorder (OCD) 	SUPERIOR LONGITUDINAL FASCICULUS (SLF) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ADHD
PARA-HIPPOCAMPUS <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Schizotypal disorder • Insomnia disorder 	LATERAL VENTRICLES <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Schizotypal disorder 	CORPUS CALLOSUM <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Schizotypal disorder 	SEPTUM PELLUCIDUM <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Schizotypal disorder
BASAL FOREBRAIN NUCLEI <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alzheimer's 	ANTERIOR PITUITARY GLAND <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Anxiety disorders 	CEREBELLUM <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Somatic Symptom disorder • Huntington's disease 	RETROSPLENIAL AREA <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conversion disorder

References for region of interest research

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User Groups

EEG - interpreting data

Neurologist	Neurophysiologist	Functional diagnostics doctor	Neuropathologist	Neurology specialist	Specialised consultant	Clinical neurophysiologist	Neurophysiology technician
Poland	Ukraine	Russia	Russia	Mexico	Nigeria	USA	Ireland
Romania	Italy			Germany			Saudi Arabia
Serbia	Denmark						
Latvia							
Hungary							
Bulgaria							
Ukraine							
Spain							
Italy							
Greece							
Malta							
Australia							
New Zealand							
Argentina							
Brazil							
South Africa							
Sweden							
France							
Belgium							
Luxembourg							
USA							
Canada							
Egypt							
Saudi Arabia							

EEG - carries out the procedure

Electroradiology technician	Lab technician	Neurologist	EEG technician	Clinical neurophysiologist	Neurophysiology specialist	Nurse assistance	Neurophysio-pathology technician	Nurse specialised in EEG
Poland	Romania	Latvia Spain France Switzerland	Hungary Bulgaria Russia Portugal Greece New Zealand Argentina Brazil Mexico South africa Denmark Finland France USA	Croatia UK	Spain	Spain	Italy	Brazil Finland

EEG - carries out the procedure (continued)

Technologist	Biomedical technologists	Physician	Specialist in neurology	Neuropediatrician	Psychiatrist	Psychotherapist	Neurophysiology technician
Nigeria Sweden Finland USA Canada Egypt Saudi Arabia	Sweden	Sweden	Germany	Switzerland Belgium	Switzerland	Switzerland	Ireland

MRI - interpreting data

Radiologist	Radiologist (continued)		Diagnostic radiologist	Interventional radiologist	Neuroradiologist
Romania	Nigeria		Bulgaria	Bulgaria	Argentina
Slovenia	Denmark				
Latvia	Sweden				
Hungary	Finland				
Bulgaria	France				
Ukraine	Belgium				
Russia	Luxembourg				
Estonia	Germany				
Lithuania	Switzerland				
Italy	Monaco				
Greece	USA				
Malta	Canada				
Australia	UK				
Argentina	Ireland				
Brazil	Israel				
Mexico	Egypt				
South africa	UAE				
Nigeria	Saudi Arabia				

MRI - carries out the procedure

Deuroimaging doctors	Engineer in radiology	Radiographer	Radiologist	Nurse assistance	Technician	biomedical engineers assistance	radiation safety specialist assistance	physicians specialised in imaging diagnostics	imaging diagnostic technicians	MRI technologist
Romania	Slovakia	Latvia Australia South africa Nigeria Denmark Sweden UK Ireland Israel	Ukraine Russia Greece Brazil Mexico France Belgium Luxembourg USA	Ukraine	Estonia Lithuania Italy Argentina France Switzerland	Estonia	Estonia	Spain Germany	spain New Zealand	South africa USA Canada Egypt

Ultrasound

Electroradiology technician	Sonographer	Radiographer	Technician	Ultrasound doctor	Biomedical engineers assistance	Radiation safety specialist assistance	Radiologist
Poland	Serbia Hungary Italy New Zealand South Africa Nigeria France Belgium Luxembourg USA Canada UK Ireland	Latvia Bulgaria Australia UK Ireland Israel	Bulgaria Saudi Arabia	Ukraine Russia	Estonia	Estonia	Lithuania Australia Mexico France Germany Monaco Saudi Arabia

Ultrasound continued

Physician	Imaging diagnostic technicians	Neurophysiopathology technician	Specialist with expertise in the anatomy of the region being explored	Doctor	Midwife	Obstetricians
Lithuania Spain	Spain	Italy	Belgium Germany	Germany UK	Ireland	Ireland

